

The Role of Ergonomics and UX Design in the field of Biohacking or Open-sourced Biotechnology

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Abstract: The field of biohacking, although nascent, has had a fair share of controversy in the recent past. This is mainly due to an influx of snake oil salesmen trying to peddle unproven supplements. This field, pioneered by former NASA scientist Jo Zayner, George F Church & Preston Estep from Harvard, and Open-source movement activists like Quinn Wilton, aimed at making Biotechnology and gene modification tools accessible, open-sourced, and available to the general public for the greater good of humanity. Since this field requires a setup of mini labs in people's homes, kitchens, and garages, we obviously understand the need for biosafety ergonomics, as well as instructions to handle bioreactors and conduct experiments require UI; therefore, there is an inevitable need for UCD principles in that area.

Practical Implications: This paper will showcase a UI designed for one such use case and talk about how an incubator and autoclave can be prepared at home using off-the-shelf examples with live examples of growing limestone bacteria. We will talk about some best practices required for the same. The other aim of this paper is to increase awareness of this area so that more people can pick this up and conduct experiments.

Keywords: Biohacking; DIY Biotechnology; Gene Modifications; Mobile AR; Proteomics.

1. Introduction

The field of biohacking is relatively new, with the term being introduced into the mainstream around 2005 (Gruber, 2019). Terms like Do-it-Yourself Biology became part of the hacker culture. The field, however, is very old; early biotechnologists started work in small labs, and some of them within their own homes, the biggest example being that of Kiran Mazumdar Shaw, who started her firm Biocon from her own home's garage, where she started extracting Papain from papaya and sold it to restaurants to help them tenderize meat. With the advent of Open source activists like Jo Zayner and Quinn Wilton the movement gained momentum, the former quit their job at the Astrobiology department in NASA and went on to found the firm ODIN Genetics that sells open source toolkits to teach Gene modification techniques to anyone interested, the site also provides courses to individuals who are interested to pick up this area Franco (2024). ODIN Genetics is advised

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by George Church, a renowned biotechnology professor from Harvard University, whose student, Preston Estep, made international news for creating a DIY COVID-19 vaccine using ingredients that can be assembled in a kitchen.

Due to the very nature of this field, biosafety is critical, and so are UX Design principles, as there is an obvious need for UI to provide instructions to the users. In this paper, we will present one such UI that aims to open-source methods to teach people to assemble DIY vaccines for tackling STIs/STDs by genetically modifying probiotics and showcase how people can make their own autoclave and incubators at home using off the shelf equipments. We will also discuss some best practices while designing UI and how to follow UCD principles for UI related to biohacking.

2. Biohacking

The movement of open-sourcing biotechnology to the masses for the greater good of society is called biohacking or DIY biotechnology. As discussed earlier, there are multiple pioneers in this field. We will look at a summary of their work, who they are, and their publications covering their work in the table below ([Table 1](#)).

Table 1. List of famous DIY Biotechnologists

S NO	Scientist	Achievement	Reference
1	Jo Zayner	Established ODIN Genetics, DIY Covid Vaccine, Gut microbiome hacking	Simons (2021)
2	Preston Estep	DIY Covid Vaccines	Estep & Church (2020)
3	Meredith Patterson	Open-Source Insulin Project	Ikemoto (2017)
4	Marc Dusseiller	Founder of Hackteria Network	Magrini (2014)
5	Kiran Majumdar Shaw	Started Biocon from her garage by isolating Papin from Papaya	Jayaraman (2005)

3. Role of Ergonomics in Biohacking

Safety is the top priority in any field. In this area of biohacking, just like traditional wet labs and chemistry labs, there has to be a set of protocols that need to be followed to ensure biosafety. This is crucial as wet labs have sterile hoods where the chances of contamination are less; however, household environments are not that secure in terms of biosafety. We need to ensure biosafety to ensure the experiments are successful via avoiding contamination as much as possible, also to ensure the experimenter is safe and secure. The following points need to be followed while conducting such experiments:

- **Protocols for Workbench area:** Keep the area for biohacking experiments separate from the rest of the areas in the home; do not mix the equipment. For example, the pressure cooker that doubles as an autoclave should never be used for cooking; it should also be stored separately.
- **Clothing & Safety Protocols:** Always use PPE, wear masks preferably N95 or respirators with P2, P3 filters and A1 or A2 cartridges, wear goggles and rubber gloves (preferably single use). Always conduct your experiments in full shoes, a lab coats and use a spray sanitizer before and after your experiments.
- **Protocols for Experiment Manuals:** Keep the instructions handy, printed or on voice command-based UI, as the gloves will prevent the users from registering touches on the screens.
- **Storage Protocols:** Always store the equipment in a cool and dry area, keep the used Agar plates in a regular fridge, discard any waste in separate bags marked as biohazard, and do not mix it with regular waste while discarding them.

4. Role of User-Centered Design in Biohacking

UCD is critical to biohacking, mainly to provide proper instructions to users and ensure that the user’s problems are addressed before they begin working in the environment. It is critical to provide instructions to the user in an accurate manner. Printed instruction manuals on a clipboard are the go-to preference in labs, due to the nature of the environment, paper can get smudged due to water and other reagents. Instructions on a mobile phone are not a good idea, and gloves will prevent touches from being registered. The users need to use the instructions on specific templates. The following protocols need to be followed for designing the UI with instructions:

- **Device protocols:** It is preferred to use instructions printed on paper with a splash guard. If we have to use mobiles or tablets, ensure they can be mounted on tripods or other mounts for the user to view them, and ensure they have voice command modes enabled.
- **UI Protocols:** The colors should operate in both light and dark mode, as some steps of the experiment should be done in the dark; the fonts should be at least 16 points and legible, the instructions are better placed in a landscape mode with audio enabled, and the interface should also have voice playback enabled.
- **UCD Protocols:** Regularly reach out to users in various online forums, to understand how they conduct their experiments and conduct interviews for the same, take photos of their lab setups, and provide clear-cut instructions in the UI on how to set up the lab.

5. Examples of Biohacking in a Garage setup

In this section, we will illustrate two examples of Biohacking that can be done in a garage. In the first one, we will look at a Mobile AR app that teaches people to assemble lactobacillus vector vaccines from the comfort of their homes to tackle STIs & STDs.

6. DIY STI Vaccines using Lactobacillus as a Vector Aided by a Mobile AR application

Lactobacillus strains are a good and easy vector that can be manipulated using plasmids to produce antibodies for a variety of diseases like Covid-19 (Villena et al., 2021), influenza (Nishihira et al., 2018), STIs and STDs like Herpes (Vilhelmova-Ilieva et al., 2022), HPV (Adachi et al., 2010), gonorrhea (Gnaman et al., 2020), etc. A plasmid can be printed easily and transported. The strains of Lactobacillus are available online along with their growth media. We made a mobile AR app to guide users on how to assemble these vaccines from the comfort of their home. We have included screenshots of the application in the images below. (Figure 1)

Figure 1. Screenshots from the Mobile AR App for DIY Lactobacillus Vaccines

7. DIY Incubator and growing Limestone bacteria at home

We isolated Actinobacter, Cephalosporium and Staphylococcus Aureus species from a limestone growth in an urban environment using a homemade autoclave which was made using a pressure cooker, we also prepared a homemade incubator using a thermocol box with flash lights and fan for heat and humidity, the temperature was maintained at 23 degrees C and 87% humidity, the temperature and humidity was measured using a store brought digital clock that showed these features, the below images showcase what can be achieved using minimal effort, post 3 days we saw microbial growth in all the plates, we have included images for all of them below (Figure 2 and Figure 3).

Figure 2. A: Melted Agar in Autoclaved Plates; B: Agar Poured into Petri Dishes for Cooling Down.
C: DIY Homemade Incubator in a Thermocol Box; D: Staphylococcus Aureus Growth in Agar.
E: Actinobacter Growth in Agar; F: Cephalosporium Growth in Agar

Figure 3. Microscopy Images of A: Staphylococcus Aureus; B: Cephalosporium;
C: Actinobacter; D: ESAW TM-5.0 TRINOCULAR Microscope, 40X-2500X Mag

8. Conclusions and Future Work

In conclusion, we would like to highlight the ease of acquiring skills in this area and how straightforward it is to learn and demonstrate them. In the future, we would like to conduct a Usability Test on the designed applications and look at the area of DIY plant biotechnology movement and how it can help farmers improve crop yield. We would like to conclude by saying every UX Designer should become a DIY Biotechnologist, but should not be influenced by the snake oil salesmen in this area.

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